

Deliverable D5.3

Third annual report on coordination and outreach

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WP Leaders	Tommi Nyrönen (6. CSC), Dylan Spalding (6, CSC)		
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Authors	Rob Hooft (21. HRI), Dylan Spalding (6, CSC)		
Contributors	Jeroen Belien (21, HRI), Tommi Nyrönen (6, CSC), Anna Hagwall (8. UU)		
Acknowledgements	[name surname (acronyms)]		
Reviewers	Jordi Rambla (CRG), Tobias Petersen (NGC)		

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1. Executive Summary

This report describes the coordination and outreach activities performed by work package 5, and collaborating work packages, since D5.2—Second annual report on coordination and outreach¹, towards the establishment of a federated infrastructure for access to genomic and associated phenotypic data.

Over the reporting period (01/10/2024 - 01/10/2025) existing coordination and communication methods have been changed to address issues and risks that have been identified, which includes:

- Establishment of a prioritized and limited list of features that will be worked on in order to focus the attention of all participants in the project on achieving maximum value.
- Prioritization of components needed by the Genome of Europe project, which is expected to deliver the first data into the infrastructure that GDI builds.
- Step-wise realisation of the infrastructure, in an agile fashion, by synchronization of small steps in the realisation of the node deployments.

At the start of the reporting period milestone 8 was achieved, which required the planning of a demonstrable user story and associated coordination with work package 3 and participating nodes. After the achievement of milestone 8, the technical planning has focused on establishing a fixed set of technical capabilities that is to be rolled out over all operational nodes by the end of the project, this was named the February Feature Freeze, FFF and defines the maximally attainable product (MAP) of the Pillar II activities in GDI. This MAP can then be used to be linked to the business capabilities as defined by Pillars I & III, as well as 1+MG, to identify any gaps and hence mitigation strategies.

In terms of outreach, GDI, as a driver project of GA4GH, has been represented at GA4GH meetings, and in the GA4GH Steering Committee. GDI carefully collaborates with the Genome of Europe (GoE) project, to which GDI will form the basis of their technical infrastructure, and conversely the GoE data will be the first real data that will be added in many GDI countries to the infrastructure. GDI also has helped define the B1MGplus project that will lead to the incorporation of the legal person that will

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13987106>

run the operational Human genomics infrastructure for 1+MG and in the mean time will facilitate the operation of the 1+MG working groups. To maximise the impact of GDI, and realise the vision of interconnected domain specific data spaces, GDI has continued to participate and collaborate with other infrastructures and projects, both at European and global level, to ensure that the solutions being developed and deployed by GDI are interoperable with these other infrastructures and projects. Within 1+MG, we also intensified collaboration with the Genome of Europe project (GoE) that is now active, as well as interaction with the new B1MGplus project.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise select 'No'. For more details of project outcomes, see [here](#)]

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No

<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers (e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 5</p> <p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	<p>No</p>

3. Methods

Pillar II has 4 work packages:

- WP3 to support the progression of nodes through the three phases—onboarding, deployment, and operational as well as software development;
- WP4 for European level operations which defines the SOPs, develops the User Portal, and operations for the operational infrastructure;
- WP5 for technical coordination, training, and outreach;
- WP6 for data management and technical implementation of the data governance

Pillar II is tasked with the technical deployment of the infrastructure as defined by 1+MG, and WP5 coordinates the different WPs in Pillar II to support this, as well as facilitates communication and interactions between Pillar II and Pillars I & III to ensure the technical infrastructure supports the required data governance and sustainability from Pillar I, and the use cases and innovative solutions (such as federated analysis and learning) as defined by Pillar III. WP5 facilitates the transition of the nodes through the three phases of maturity; from onboarding, through deployment, to operational. As such, WP5 needs to provide the technical coordination to support the progress of the nodes towards operational, provide the training and knowledge transfer as required to support the nodes, and outreach to stakeholders and associated projects, organisations, and infrastructures. WP5 has been arranging meetings, workshops, email and Slack channels, as well as project management and repositories to facilitate this. As the specifics of the core infrastructure due to be deployed become clearer, specific training requirements can be identified and addressed, as well as more general training from production nodes to the deployment and onboarding nodes. Each node that aims to deploy GDI infrastructure is required to identify their aspirational phase, and the timeline to achieve that. While each node must support the five functionalities (data discovery, data access and management, storage and interfaces, data reception, processing) as defined by B1MG / 1+MG², the node may choose how to implement them within the governance framework as defined by Pillar I. This is to support the diversity in the national policies for genomics and health data, as well as funding processes. A challenge for WP5 is to ensure that this national diversity is supported within the GDI and does not negatively affect the FAIRness of the infrastructure as a whole. The early milestones, such as the release of the GDI Starter Kit³ and the deployment of it across 7 vanguard nodes in milestone 7, help identify the gaps and requirements for the infrastructure and enable the nodes to investigate the technical standards and implementations on their own physical infrastructures.

WP5 works to ensure that the different work packages and Pillars in GDI support the 1+MG vision, and has over the last 12 months focused on establishing a clear vision of the expected end results for operational nodes, and monitoring progress towards that end result.

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6089582>

³ <https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/starter-kit>

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Technical Coordination

4.1.1 Github

The GDI project extensively makes use of GitHub to track development of technical infrastructure and also to develop the Standard Operating Procedures (SOP). The GDI organisation on Github⁴ has 45 repositories that are worked on by 106 people.

Agile processes used to be managed through Zenhub accounts before; in the past year the management of the GDI project was no longer allowed non-profit use of Zenhub, hence paid accounts were needed for work on the issues. A review of preferences of the Product Owners, Task Force facilitators, and Pillar and WP leads was performed, and the outcome supported the decision to abandon Zenhub and move the data from Zenhub into the Github environment; where necessary this is supported through documents in the project's Google Shared Drive.

4.1.2 Pillar II meetings

Monthly meetings of Pillar II have continued throughout the third year of the project, attracting an attendance between 50-80 project members every time. During this period, the process that was started at the end of year two was continued in which every node in the project has been invited to present a brief overview of their organisation; this was organised as three 20 minute slots in the monthly meetings over a period of time, during which other routine topics like progress in the work packages were limited to the absolutely necessary. The node presentations were recorded and the recordings made available in the project Google drive space. The aim was to try and build understanding between the nodes about the specific issues faced by different nodes, as well as to clarify the diversity of the deployments in the project, and to try and build different collaborations between the nodes where similar issues exist. There was also the opportunity to feedback on the specific standards and products included in the Starter Kit. An increased understanding of the nodes was achieved, as well as maintaining a high level of participation in the meetings, however building collaborations between nodes was less successful, and will be addressed via node 'buddy-ups' in year 4.

Since May 2025, when all nodes had presented, the main topic of focus for the meetings has shifted to scoping discussions surrounding the February Feature Freeze (see 4.1.10); making sure the understanding of what is needed for a coherent implementation is shared between the nodes in the project and thereby putting effort in equalling the level of implementation in all nodes that have the ambition of becoming operational by the end of the project. The meetings also have a regular agenda item for Pillar II work packages, Pillars I & III, and the task forces to report back and request support of help from other members of Pillar II to try and ensure effective communication between Pillar II and other stakeholders. Participation was variable in the Pillar II meeting for the task forces

⁴ <https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure>

and different Pillars and the size and scope of the meeting is not necessarily ideal for in depth discussion about inter-pillar issues, so specific monthly cross Pillar (X-Pillar) meetings have been set up with key participants from each of the Pillars and task forces.

4.1.3 Paris workshop

No Pillar II workshop was held in the reporting period. The next workshop is planned for 15-17 October in Paris, France. Special focus will be given to the implementation of the functionality for the “February Feature Freeze” (see 4.1.10) and the actual use of the infrastructure for the support of the Genome of Europe project with some or all of its use cases.

4.1.4 Data Inclusion Scenarios

A hybrid workshop was held on October 1st 2024 to discuss the WP6 prepared document “Data Inclusion Scenarios in 1+MG”⁵ with the GDI Governance panel. Approximately 25 participants were physically present in Brussels, several others joined on-line. The workshop was structured as 5 independent *decision briefs* in which document chapter authors presented their analysis of different options and consequences. Results of each discussion were added as sections to the chapters in the document and form additional guidance for (national) implementation of the infrastructure.

4.1.5 Workshop Technical implications of the governance

An online workshop with approximately 65 participants was held at the end of the previous reporting period, on September 13, 2024, with the subject “Technical Implications of Governance”⁶ and as its goal to bring together Pillar II and Pillar I to discuss in detail the expectations from the proposed governance in Pillar I from the technical infrastructure built by Pillar II. The workshop was prepared by the careful identification of possible technical implications in the governance documentation by a selected group of Pillar II participants, and in the workshop itself, after quick introduction of the governance principles, a prioritized list of the implications was discussed. After the workshop, an analysis⁷ was created of the follow up actions that would be necessary to implement the governance in detail as well as suggested changes to the governance. This document was later used as input for the February Feature Freeze (see 4.1.10).

4.1.6 Workshop Data inclusion implications of the governance

An online workshop “*Data Inclusion consequences of the 1+MG Governance*” was held on January 22, 2025⁸. More than fifty participants discussed prioritized topics on the consequences of the data governance documentation from Pillar I on the data inclusion into GDI; both important for Pillar II as infrastructure builders as well as for Pillar III delivering the data from the different use cases. The structure of the workshop was similar to the workshop on technical implications of the governance,

⁵ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1YfHBPQzSuxDt2BLUqyW_cKSsMbbQySUftqokmacxUiU/edit?usp=sharing

⁶ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ZiK5XE7fseNbQsvtU_RhNo_2uN5vcOncWPbphIGyRoo/edit?usp=sharing

⁷ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1TiLYVeaJJRHYYDggeoThCrSr3aOXFyfrz9NzQKvoG2s/edit?usp=sharing>

⁸ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1K5DWkdQhPIV-KSk3HNB_rNQ1CUzZxbl-WoEo_sSyDbs/edit?usp=sharing

including the preparation⁹ and followup. The results of this workshop have also been used as input for the February Feature Freeze (see 4.1.10)

4.1.7 Workshop on FitSM and Standard Operating Procedures

Once the February Feature Freeze (FFF - see 4.1.10) had been determined, a workshop was held on May 27, 2025¹⁰ with 29 participants. The main aim was to help the nodes targeting operational status to consider the service management requirements, plus the necessary Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) that are necessary to ensure the efficient, effective, and legally compliant operation of the services deployed at each node. The workshop focussed on the use of the FitSM¹¹ framework, which is a lightweight service management framework for federated services, which is compatible with the ISO/IEC 20000-1 standard for service management. One of the main results was the closer integration of task 4.2 (European Operations), which proposed the FitSM framework, and task 4.3 which is responsible for the definition and management of the SOPs. The workshop also served as a way to try and increase node engagement.

4.1.8 Continued work and outcome of task forces

During year three, the productionization task force continued its work and delivered a model describing the expectations that the project has of a TRL-9 level tool. Nodes can use this model to determine the level of their expectation in the selection of available alternative implementations.

The PID task force has established a prioritized list of items that require a consistent persistent identifier. In the prioritization, implementation of these PIDs has been put off for after the completion of the GDI project. The PID task force thereby completed what was needed.

The metadata squad continued its work to determine the metadata required for GDI, and to try to understand the different requirements and use cases across different nodes and other data spaces and infrastructures. As input for its work the results from Brno workshop session on metadata were used and extended resulting in a metadata squad charter containing an inventory as well as prioritisation of the various types of metadata within 1+MG/GDI. Most of the metadata squad work is closely linked to task 8.2 where the focus was on delivery of v1.0 of the 1+MG harmonised minimal data model (including metadata for submission of datasets based on HealthDCAT-AP). This v1.0 was delivered in February 2025 and currently is being updated with crosswalks between major used ontologies (e.g. SNOMED CT, ICD10/11, LOINC, NCIT) as well as major used other data models (e.g. Beacon v2) and is currently being documented. Next the 1+MG WG11 on infectious diseases provided the Minimal data model for infectious diseases (MDID) which is being merged into v1.0 via a review process set-up via the 1+MG WG3/GDI tasks/B1MGplus expert meetings. The metadata squad also started working on the GDI ELSI related metadata for which a first workshop was organised which will be given follow-up workshops taking into account the updated 1+MG/GDI governance (see 4.1.13 and coordinated via the recently started B1MGplus CSA).

⁹ https://docs.google.com/document/d/12mtrlaqUdQ-JH9Xy9BpMj7J_ZV5q85mV-qL_V5sq5eY/edit?usp=sharing

¹⁰ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1xvL-DxKVd1NLil_9aAqbY5o6tQ1rkEnTx3CPfhc2DYUwU/edit?tab=t.o#heading=h.g8nhlzqg3egn

¹¹ <https://www.fitsm.eu/>

The Data Protection and Security Task Force sent out two questionnaires¹² to all product owners regarding how their product conforms to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) principles and the requirements of the draft Cybersecurity Resilience Act (CRA), and on a more technical level using the Open Worldwide Application Security Project (OWASP) Application Security Verification Standard (ASVS) checklist as a way of checking the security of the products technically, e.g. helping ensure the product will pass penetration tests. However progress has been slow due to the task force facilitator leaving the GDI project, and no other facilitator has been found. However, the establishment of the Security and Data Protection Committee, as well as the technical deployment being decided via the February Feature Freeze (FFF - see Section 4.1.10) further progress on this should be made.

Both the Authentication and Authorisation (AAI) and Application Programming Interface (API) Task Forces have been blocked by the definition of the FFF, and analysing the effects of the change to decentralised controllership and support for dynamic consent (section 4.1.13). However both task forces still exist and are able to address requirements now that the effect of these governance changes has been confirmed.

4.1.9 Milestone 8

Milestone 8 was achieved on November 20, 2024 and a presentable video of the achievement was produced and released March 21, 2025 (D3.6¹³). This milestone is very important as the basis of the February Feature Freeze (FFF - Section 4.1.10) which aimed to clarify the functionality that should be expected from all operational nodes by the end of the project.

4.1.10 February Feature Freeze

In order for the technical infrastructure to work towards the same goal in all nodes, and to prevent the risks of so-called "scope creep", it was decided at the beginning of the third year to work towards a fixed definition of the functionality by February 2025. This was dubbed the February Feature Freeze (FFF). The process of defining the FFF started with the User Journey¹⁴ document initiated by Pillar III, but with contributions from Pillars I & II. Several meetings were organised, starting on the 4th¹⁵ of February, to identify the exact expected functionality and the gaps that needed to be filled to achieve that functionality. This was finalised by a face-to-face meeting¹⁶ in Helsinki on 23rd / 24th April, with the Product Owners and associated Task Force facilitators to identify what was technically achievable, by April 2026, by the end of GDI, and what was not technically achievable in the GDI timescales from a Product Owner perspective.

¹² <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1izot2pq8KC1pTSPOTaHrISETrs9hvuwn/edit?gid=1001694747#gid=1001694747>

¹³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15124376>

¹⁴ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1QDeRvtWWrhMj2BrzpetxgwwzupQfo-Rx8Xd53QigTWBs/edit?usp=sharing>

¹⁵ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1lnR_bBatmM5XMc87_oNEOADywbQapRQBh314uvE7aws/edit?tab=t.0#heading-h.cdwfod8e3zq2

¹⁶ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1cxukXinHN2KJhtILY2_S3jvQmvDwOvvyfYonHvuJ1qY/edit?tab=t.0#heading-h.g8nhlzzgq3egn

The results of this were then presented¹⁷ at the GDI cross-pillar meeting, and to the management board on 20th May, with comments open on the proposal for 2 weeks, however no adverse comments were received resulting in the proposal being approved by the Management Board as the blueprint for the technical deployment by the end of GDI by . After approval, this was presented to the whole of Pillar II at the Pillar II meeting on 11th June¹⁸.

Concurrently Pillar I GOV group were voting on an interim proposal for the sustainability of GDI in the near term, with a longer term proposal to support interoperability with EHDS. The result of this was a change in the controllership for the data disclosure process, with the vote for the interim implementation recommending decentralised controllership with dynamic consent as legal base. While Pillar II was aware of the voting process, Pillar II had to continue to support the current data governance as it existed at the time, and the result of the vote has had a significant effect on the FFF definition. When a survey was carried out for the Node Alignment Workshop (Section 4.1.13) 7 nodes indicated that this vote would have no affect on their deployment plans, however 4 nodes indicated they could support fully decentralised access management technical deployment which does not conform to the 1+MGambition or the data governance as defined by Pillar I, and the other 3 nodes did not answer the question on the data access management deployment.

4.1.11 Change management - RFC process

The Request For Change (RFC) process that has been drafted has been paused during the third year as work was concentrated on aligning the WP4 tasks 4.2 (European Level Operations) and task 4.3 (Standard Operating Procedures), especially in outreach to the nodes to try and increase engagement (e.g by FitSM drop-in sessions and a Task 4.2/4.3 workshop¹⁹). T4.2 has decided to use the FitSM²⁰ framework for service management, and once that framework has started to be implemented by the nodes the RFC process will be refined and updated to ensure it aligns with both FitSM and the continued development of the SOPs.

4.1.12 Sovereign documentation system

LNDS, as prospective host of the Genome EDIC, has set up a Nextcloud²¹ system where GDI, and in the future the Genome EDIC, securely keep sensitive documents about the infrastructure. First to do there is the Risk Assessment Matrix (see 4.3); in the future it could also be used for other documentation of the infrastructure, such as the SOPs

4.1.13 Node Alignment Workshop

A Node Alignment Workshop²² was held on 1st September 2025. In advance, a survey was done of technical and governance functions in each node, to establish the best path towards the

¹⁷ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1_tuYUf3GdU6aaguUJC_Khb01rRtqilUY/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=109542590062113651245&rtfpof=true&sd=true

¹⁸ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1Guz6-e0aFFhg6dXAX0i-_b9jOMcYIYGA/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=109542590062113651245&rtfpof=true&sd=true

¹⁹ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1xvLDxKVd1NLiLoaAqbY5o6tQ1rkEnTx3CPfhc2DYUwU/edit?tab=t.o#heading=h.g8nhlzqg3eqn>

²⁰ <https://www.fitsm.eu/>

²¹ <https://nextcloud.com/>

²² <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1cExoAwgcZwGrrJsYToilNe6Ea6eNURIQlxgDzySybFM/edit?tab=t.o#heading=h.gliizdlppwdw>

implementation of the data governance. 18 nodes (partially) responded to that survey, giving a good idea on how the developments in the remainder of the project can be aligned, and what needs to be done to couple the nodes into a single infrastructure²³. During the workshop, 13 nodes also gave a brief presentation of their implementation choices and of what they need to implement this. The results of the workshop have been helping us to define common needs and paths (including any tasks for the different task forces), and refine priorities for the remaining development of tools, features and standard operating procedures.

4.1.14 Governance changes from Pillar I

During the reporting year, the governance panel of the project, meeting monthly with Pillar I, has concluded that a central decision about and legal responsibility for the data disclosure decision can not be put in an EDIC under European law. It was then decided that, as a short term solution, the GDI project will work on the implementation of decentralised responsibility for the data disclosure. This has small but significant consequences, which are being analysed to be supported by the February Feature Freeze (4.1.10), which will become the Maximum Attainable Product (MAP).

The Node Alignment Workshop (4.1.13) requested feedback from the nodes regarding any effect they saw on their plan with the change in responsibility for data disclosure, as well as the support for dynamic consent. An initial result is that in terms of hosting a service to manage data access, some nodes would like this to be a function of the User Portal (i.e. as demonstrated in MS8), but some want to host and manage this service locally. Analysis on how to support this hybrid deployment, and its effect on the work of the AAI, API, Data Protection and Security task forces, and the work of Tasks 4.2 (European Operations) and 4.3 (Standard Operating Procedures) are being determined.

4.2 Outreach

4.2.1 Genome of Europe

The Genome of Europe (GoE) project kicked off in November 2024. There is strong collaboration between this project and GDI: Not only are several of the use cases in the Genome of Europe project also part of the GDI project, but conversely several of the GDI infrastructure experts are part of the data management work package of GoE (WP4). GDI WP5 representatives (CRG team members from EGA and the GA4GH Beacon working group) attended the GoE WP5 (Sequencing) and WP6 (Use Cases) meetings as part of the outreach. The focus on supporting GoE data and use cases prior to the end of the GDI project has enabled a focus on the short term project requirements and deliverables, while still moving towards attaining the full 1+MG ambition post GDI. To avoid complexities of the inclusion of personal data in the Beacon service before the final governance organisation is in place, close discussions between GoE and GDI have resulted in the intermediate solution of pre-aggregated data for data discovery.

²³ <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/18iudbrHLeRP3H7C7eHuvIPTKed7gHVkM/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=109542590062113651245&rtpof=true&sd=true>

4.2.2 GA4GH

WP5 and other Pillar II representatives (Tommi Nyronen, Dylan Spalding, Melissa Konopko, Salvador Capella and Jordi Rambla) have attended the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) Connect meeting²⁴ in Boston between 1st and 4th April 2025, and a delegation will attend the Connect and Plenary meetings in Uppsala in October 2025. WP5 also represents the GDI Driver Project on the Steering Committee, which helps ensure that approved standards reflect the needs of the GDI project, and more widely help ensure the European viewpoint is represented. An example is the requirements for improvements to the GA4GH Passport standard, where LS Login POs and WP5 representatives describe zero-trust requirements and verifiable credentials²⁵ support.

GDI participants are also co-leads within the GA4GH Beacon²⁶ API development, and this helps ensure that the evolving requirements of GDI and 1+MG are represented in the development of the Beacon standard, and in the implementations needed to ensure that a standard is approved by the GA4GH steering committee.

4.2.3 B1MGplus

B1MGplus started in February 2025 and kicked-off on March 11th 2025. Closely aligned with the activities in GDI Pillar I, the work needed for EDIC establishment will be accelerated through work in B1MGplus WP2, and uses of the infrastructure for healthcare including health economics get a boost from work in B1MGplus WP3. B1MGplus WP4 works on establishing the data requirements. GDI Pillar II carefully monitors the progress in these work packages so that necessary adaptations in the technical infrastructure can be considered.

4.2.4 ECCB

GDI was presented as part of the ELIXIR presentation 'Using ELIXIR supported infrastructure to access human Genomic data at scale'²⁷ at the European Conference on Computational Biology²⁸ (ECCB) at Turku between 16th and 20th September 2024.

4.2.5 EOSC4Cancer

WP5 has been involved in the EOSC4Cancer project, especially with the demonstrations of data access to cancer data. A specific example of how the core GDI infrastructure can support other EU projects are the EOSC4Cancer deliverable D1.2²⁹ (Data Access Interoperability) where the GDI User Portal was used to demonstrate data discovery and data access application, and the use of visas issued by the GDI User Portal to access cancer data in two different EOSC4Cancer participants SPEs, CSC and UMCG.

²⁴ <https://www.ga4gh.org/document/ga4gh-april-connect-2025-meeting-report/>

²⁵ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ugTxH_mAoAmoKyxHU2MRkYDXJndrcU/edit

²⁶ <https://www.ga4gh.org/product/beacon-api/>

²⁷ <https://f1000research.com/slides/13-1167>

²⁸ <https://eccb2024.fi/>

²⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15638951>

4.2.6 EHDS

The European Health Data Space (EHDS) regulation³⁰ was accepted and entered into force on March 26, 2025. Genomic data will be falling under the EHDS as from March 26, 2031. Several of the participants in Pillar II are following the HealthData@EU and TEHDAS2 outcomes, and through our communication with Pillar I, where governance is aligned with the future implementation of EHDS, any changes needed in technical implementation in Pillar II are identified.

4.2.7 EOSC-Entrust

GDI is continuing to monitor outputs from the EOSC-ENTRUST project, and is helping to input into the requirements via both the ELIXIR coordination and the ELIXIR Federated Human Genomics theme (including participation from several participants in GDI like BSC, CRG and EMBL) as a catalyst for European TRE provision (driver 1) in EOSC-ENTRUST WP7 and associated deliverable report D7.1³¹. This interaction with EOSC-ENTRUST aims to ensure the alignment between the outputs of EOSC-ENTRUST and the requirements of GDI, especially with respect to the technologies used and the data governance.

4.2.8 International Infrastructures and Projects

In the past year, the CANDLE project³² (coordinated by Health-RI) was started with the goal to bring Cancer Data Nodes online in EU countries, playing a role in the provisioning of cancer data for the EHDS, from the EU Cancer Mission. Since genetics plays an important role in cancer data, connections between GDI and CANDLE were immediately established and will require continued attention.

The European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA) and its Federation (FEGA) members continue to contribute to GDI on aspects that expand all Pillars. FEGA keeps aligning their strategy and technology to be compatible with GDI requirements and providing the base technology for some GDI nodes.

4.3 Risk Assessment Matrix

The prospective Risk Assessment processes have been first described in D5.1 two years ago. Until mid 2025, the focus of the technical implementation has been on achieving operational levels. Security and Data Protection by Design have been pervasive in the project. Now that the project is approaching the operationalisation, the systemic processes of risk assessment need to be operationalised as well.

Since the systemic analysis in a Risk Assessment Matrix can lead to highly sensitive information about potential attacks and weaknesses, the collaboration surrounding this process requires tough measures of security. It was decided that the collaboration should therefore not make use of

³⁰ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2025/327/oj/eng>

³¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14988868>

³² <https://candle-project.eu/about/the-project/>

non-european cloud services. A sovereign documentation system (see 4.1.12) and video conferencing facility was therefore set up, after verification that the system that was foreseen would be capable of dealing with the document template that had been developed during year 1 of GDI.

Workshops will be started to collectively identify the threats and risks for the infrastructure with the members of the Security and Data Protection committee as defined in MS10.

5. Results

1. Pillar II meetings concluded round of presentations of all nodes
2. Milestone 8 and video presentation of its capabilities
3. February Feature Freeze established including planning to fill all remaining gaps
4. Task forces delivered their expected documentation
5. Three X-Pillar workshops held
6. Interactions with associated infrastructures, projects, and data spaces

Point 1. The overview of operationalisation activities in each of the nodes was completed, giving us a comprehensive view of options nodes are exploring. This has kickstarted new discussions between nodes.

Point 2. Milestone 8 has been achieved, showing possibilities from the infrastructure both for the Cancer and the Infectious disease use cases. The results and experience was used to bootstrap the definition of the expected level of operations for nodes by the end of the project.

Point 3. Analysis of milestone 8, expectations about the interaction of the users with the interface as collected from Pillar III, as well as conclusions from cross-pillar workshops were used to define what gaps still needed to be filled before the end of the project. A resource planning and prioritization resulted in a Maximum Attainable Product definition which we named "February Feature Freeze".

Point 4.

The use of task forces has facilitated the generation of the necessary documentation for their respective tasks, such as the API list³³ in GitHub, and the still evolving production-readiness checklist³⁴ and non-functional requirements³⁵ that are used to determine when a node has reached production status.

Point 5. Cross-pillar workshops were held:

1. To discuss the consequences of the prospective data governance (Pillar I) for the technical implementation (Pillar II)
2. To discuss the consequences of the prospective data governance (Pillar I) for the data onboarding (Pillar II and Pillar III)

³³ <https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/api-links>

³⁴ https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1CCkixRHHXrP6bWcyohzCDg-BCIqSZ9E6nz93B_MNG7o/edit?gid=812016504#gid=812016504

³⁵ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1KzLRtgynKRYAgn1q70wabmZVfr2DBRRQIXGgR07-em4/edit?tab=t.o>

3. To discuss some open questions from WP6 (Pillar II) with the governance board (Pillar I)

Point 6. GDI is continuing to interact with associated projects, and data spaces, such as EHDS, TEHDAS2, EOSC-ENTRUST, EUCAIM, and GA4GH. This is necessary to ensure the maximum interoperability of the relevant infrastructures, and maximise the FAIRness of the data.

6. Discussion

1. Continued discussions on MVP versus maximum attainable product
2. Timing of real data in the infrastructure and the DPIA
3. Changes expected after changes in the foreseen governance
4. Consequences of delays in the establishing of the Genome EDIC

Point 1. Pillar II has strongly improved the perception of what can be achieved with the technical work during the project, the maximum attainable product (MAP). Communication with Pillar I around this MAP and the Pillar I Minimal viable product (MVP) should be intensified, coming to a common definition of a result that is both attainable and viable.

Point 2. The planning calls for the nodes that have the ambition to become operational in the project to have achieved maturity in April 2026. In parallel, component wise and integral analysis of the information security will be made. Since there are mutual dependencies between these processes, it is hard to foresee when all the Data Protection Impact Assessments will be ready that are the prerequisite of onboarding real data into the infrastructure. A suggestion has been made to start with a single user gaining access to a single real genome, so that this lock can be broken.

Point 3. Discussions on the implications of the change in governance are ongoing at high priority, but have not yet reached their final conclusion. The intended governance changes are small, but there is no complete consensus yet over the changes that implementing this will have on the technical components (e.g. who is responsible for access permission registrations, and consent management systems).

Point 4. Some processes and the exact text for (dynamic) consenting of data subjects are dependent on the establishment of the legal structure (EDIC, as foreseen). The legal analysis and subsequent necessary changes to the governance have delayed the establishment of the institute, and this may cause delays in readying the infrastructure for real data.

7. Conclusions & Impact

1. FFF
2. Collaboration with Genome of Europe.

Point 1. A lot of effort has been put in the complete analysis of all the remaining work and all the gaps. The definition of the FFF is the culmination of that work, and at the same time the guide towards the implementation that we needed for the fourth year of the project.

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Point 2. With the Genome of Europe underway for almost a year, the collaboration is starting to take shape. Genome of Europe has been selected as the main focus for the use cases to be implemented during the GDI project. Pillar II of GDI and WP4 of GoE have built a strong collaboration.

8. Next steps

1. Work towards implementation of FFF
2. Monitoring of the FFF promises
3. Risk analysis
4. Monitoring of the developments in the governance

Point 1. Implementation of the February Feature Freeze components is in full swing, and will need to continue with full force. Stepwise verification of the achievements, continuing from the first step on September 1st with pingable beacon and FAIR Data Point components, will be important.

Point 2. It is essential that Pillar I and Pillar II together establish the technical capabilities that we will be achieving, and monitor whether they are and stay in line with the expectation that 1+MG places on the project's results.

Point 3. Now that a good overview is starting to appear of the final architecture of the infrastructure and the components deployed centrally and in the nodes, the security and data protection committee with members from each node will need to start working on the threat and risk analysis.

Point 4. It still needs to be completely established whether the current FFF needs further adaptations to the changed controllership for the data disclosure. Further progress in the definition of the 1+MG data governance needs to be followed, in order to be able to adapt to any changes through adjustments in the goals of the FFF.

